

The Formation of the Competence of Preschool Educators to Prepare Children for School as A Socio-Pedagogical Necessity

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Abstract

The article presents a creative approach to the educational process in the development of preschool competencies in preschool education, to be an inquisitive, researcher, designer, to be active in fulfilling all the tasks, to improve the competence of school preparation, to achieve the design of educational processes for mastering the content of education in connection with the problem-based teaching method in the education system of the industry, information and pedagogical technologies, interactive teaching methods to create a psychological environment in which set by the State requirements for preschool education.

Keywords: competence, competent, variable program, creative experiments, pedagogical technologies, competency approach, independent learning activities,

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The new Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Preschool Education and Training” [1], which is in force in the new Republic of Uzbekistan, provides a new content of the preschool education system - a radical renewal of the educational process, creates a healthy competitive environment among organizations as well as preschool education. This is a key factor in the development of preschool education. Accordingly, educators of preschool education organizations should acquire the qualities of cooperation, initiative, entrepreneurship, creativity, research, social activism, innovative thinking in the process of higher pedagogical education. Therefore, a creative approach to the educational process in the development of educators for preschool education and the **preservation of the competence to prepare children for school**, to be inquisitive, researcher, designer, active in fulfilling all the tasks set by the State requirements for preschool education Demonstration, approach to the educational process as an experimental field, testing of new ideas and creative experiences, improvement of the system of preschool education and its content to achieve thorough and quality mastery by students of school age it is important to focus on having supply capacity.

To do this, to acquire the ability to use educational technologies in the process of preschool education, which will ensure the full mastery of the content of the State Program “First Step” [2] and its alternatives, in particular, to study the content of programs at the level of educational elements, to get acquainted with the teaching aids, didactic sources, recommendations, technological developments, algorithms, audio-video-visual aids and test kits created for educators required.

One of the most pressing issues facing preschools today is quality education for students, to achieve the effective organization of the activities of the **five centers** in the educational process in order to develop them in all respects, to prepare children for school life through the study of their imagination and initial interests and tendencies in school. Improving the quality of preschool education, creating mechanisms for its effective organization in accordance with the requirements of the time, one of the most important issues in the field of “Methods of preparing children

for school” [3] is the development of a scientific basis for the training of highly qualified professionals. It is important to study this issue in detail and develop a new model that will expand the opportunities for scientific and methodological management of preschool education.

Effective organization of the system of improving the quality of preschool education in the form of harmonized, flexible, optimized approaches, this system is a state policy for the development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, Presidential decrees and resolutions, as well as decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, should create ample opportunities for the implementation of the goals and objectives. In accordance with the state requirements for preschool education and modernized programs, the changing situation should be addressed in a timely manner by the leaders of educational institutions and the teaching staff.

The essence of the new approach to the effective organization of the preschool education process is to abandon the processes based on the old approach, which does not give the expected results in traditional education, and to:

- organization of preschool education process on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies;
- preparing children for independent learning activities;
- it is necessary to achieve the implementation of educational processes in accordance with the modern requirements of preschool education.

The emergence of a new pedagogical approach to preschool education requires a comprehensive development of students of preschool age, a differentiated and individualized competency approach to them. In organizing the process of preschool education on the basis of these approaches:

- ✓ special consideration of the interests and levels of development of students of preschool age;
- ✓ to identify the positive qualities and abilities of students of pre-school age and opportunities for their development, to identify their interests, needs, abilities, personal qualities, intellectual and intellectual characteristics;

✓ selection of tasks according to the needs, interests, abilities and capabilities of the pupil of each school age;

✓ in the process of pre-school education should take into account the individual characteristics of students of preschool age;

An important factor in the effectiveness of the preschool education process is inextricably linked with the formation of a high level of competence of educators of preschool education institutions in **preparing children for school** [4]. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks is to create a theoretical and practical basis for the process of improving the competence of educators to prepare children for quality school education, based on the effective use of modern educational technologies and educational and methodological complexes.

Reforms in the field of preschool education require the improvement of mechanisms for the effective organization of the preschool education process, i.e. the abandonment of traditional methods of this process and the experience of organizing the educational process based on democratic principles in line with socio-economic development. This in itself sets the task of identifying mechanisms for improving the quality of education through the organization and coordination of the activities of the subjects of the preschool education process, coordination and implementation on the basis of competency-based approaches.

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